

Analysis of Human Rights Violations in the Extractive Industry in Raja Ampat, Indonesia: UNGPs Framework Approach

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Abstract

The rapid growth of the nickel mining industry in Indonesia, particularly in Raja Ampat, West Papua, has encouraged significant investment from both national private companies and state-owned enterprises. However, these activities often raise human rights issues, especially those related to indigenous communities and environmental damage. This study aims to analyze human rights violations occurring in nickel mining projects in Raja Ampat, Indonesia, and to assess the extent to which the state and corporations fulfill their responsibilities based on the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs). This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. Data were collected through literature review, analysis of policy documents, human rights organization reports, as well as publications from environmental activists, academics, and affected communities. The study applies the UNGPs framework to examine three main aspects: (1) The obligations of the state to protect human rights, (2) the responsibility of corporations to respect human rights, and (3) public access to effective remedy mechanisms. Research findings indicate that the nickel mining projects in Raja Ampat, West Papua, have not fully implemented the principles of the UNGPs. The lack of transparency in the licensing process, the absence of Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC) mechanisms, and limited access to remedies for environmental, social, and economic damages are the main findings. This study recommends strengthening national human rights-based regulations, making FPIC a prerequisite for issuing mining licenses, and enforcing human rights due diligence obligations for corporations. **Keywords:** UNGPs, Human Rights, Extractive, Nickel, Raja Ampat.

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Introduction

Indonesia is a country with the largest nickel reserves in the world, accounting for around 23% of the total global reserves, or equivalent to 17.7 billion tons of nickel. These reserves are spread across several regions, including Southeast Sulawesi Province and Central Sulawesi. South Sulawesi, Maluku, North Maluku, West Papua, and Southwest Papua (ESDM, 2023). Over time, the discourse on renewable energy has been growing stronger, particularly in the automotive industry, which is driving the production of electric vehicles. One of the main components in the electric vehicle industry and the transition to renewable energy is the battery, where nickel serves as a primary raw material. As a result, global demand for nickel has increased significantly (Indonesia Data, 2024). According to data from CSULFinance, global nickel production is concentrated in eight major countries: the Philippines, New Caledonia, Russia, Canada, Australia, China, Brazil, and Indonesia. Indonesia ranks first, with an estimated production volume of 2,200,000 tons in 2024 (CSULFinance, 2024).

Table 1.1

The Eight Largest Nickel-Producing Countries in the World in 2024

(Source: Processed from the United States Geological Survey Data, 2024)

Countries	Nickel Production Estimate (Ton)
Indonesia	2.200.000
Philippines	330.000
Russia	210.000
Canada	190.000
China	120.000
Australia	110.000
New Caledonia	110.000
Brazil	77.000

The data shows that Indonesia recorded the highest nickel production among the world's major nickel-producing countries, amounting to 2,200,000 tons in 2024.

Figure 1.1

Nickel Resources and Reserves in Indonesia

(Source: Processed from Kata Data Indonesia Data (Ahdiat, 2025))

One of the regions in Indonesia with significant nickel reserves is Raja Ampat, West Papua. According to nickel resource and reserve data from Kata Data Indonesia (2025), Raja Ampat ranks fifth as an area with the largest nickel resources and reserves in Indonesia. With a population of around 70,000 people, the economic structure of Raja Ampat is still heavily dependent on the mining and extraction sectors, as recorded by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS, 2024). Nickel exploration activities in this area have been ongoing since 1967 on Gag Island and were pioneered by PT Gag Nickel (Permanadewi et al., 2017). From an economic perspective, nickel is a strategic commodity for Indonesia, especially for the Raja Ampat region, given its role in supporting the clean energy transition and the development of the electric vehicle battery industry. However, from an environmental perspective, Raja Ampat has a very sensitive terrestrial and marine ecosystem. Exploration activities and nickel mining has the potential to pose threats such as deforestation, marine sedimentation, and water pollution, which ultimately endanger coral reefs, marine biodiversity, and the livelihoods of local coastal communities. In addition, there are social and resource governance dimensions that cannot be ignored. Most of the land in West Papua, including in Raja Ampat, is customary land subject to traditional ownership systems. Raja Ampat has also been designated as a UNESCO Global Geopark since 2023.

In recent years, public attention to mining activities in Raja Ampat has grown. Local communities have expressed concerns that some mining companies do not fully comply with environmental regulations and have expanded their concession areas into Geopark zones, areas that should be protected from extractive activities (Batara, 2025). In response to community demands, the government revoked the Mining Business License (IUP) It is owned by four companies, namely PT Anugerah Surya Pratama (ASP), PT Mulia Raymond Perkasa (MRP), PT Kawei Sejahtera Mining (KSM), and PT Nurham. Nevertheless, PT Gag Nickel continues to maintain its operational permit as it is deemed to have met the Environmental Impact Assessment (AMDAL) requirements and is the only company in Raja Ampat with a Work Plan and Budget (RKAB) approved for 2025 (TEMPO, 2025). This situation raises an important question about who actually benefits the most from the exploration and exploitation of natural resources in the area.

The dilemma between economic growth and environmental protection remains an interesting topic in academic debate. This issue continues to evolve, and its relevance is becoming stronger as the global industrial landscape shifts toward renewable energy, where environmental accountability and human rights responsibilities cannot be separated from industrial practices. In response to these dynamics, this study provides a comprehensive analysis of human rights violations related to nickel mining projects in Raja Ampat and examines the extent to which the state and corporations fulfill their obligations under the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs).

This study aims to identify novelty and gaps in the literature by focusing on three main variables: first, human rights violations in the extractive industry; second, the operating context of nickel mining in Raja Ampat; and third, the implementation of the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs).

The first variable relates to human rights violations in the mining industry. Previous studies have highlighted the relationship between the extractive industry and human rights violations in Indonesia; however, none have specifically examined the case of nickel mining in Raja Ampat through the UNGPs framework. Werner (2023) identifies patterns of community rights violations caused by weak post-mining accountability in the coal sector, while Kemp (2010) emphasizes the importance of integrating human rights principles into mining water governance. Ascencio (2024) developed a theoretical framework for corporate accountability in human rights violations at the global level, and Hudayana (2020) demonstrated the link between social conflicts and human rights violations in the mining sector in Indonesia. Meanwhile, Jamin (2023) argued that regulatory changes in the mining sector have not fully protected the rights of indigenous peoples in accordance with the UNGPs. Although these studies provide valuable theoretical and empirical foundations, none specifically examine the concrete implementation of the UNGPs, which encompasses the state's duty to protect, corporate responsibility to respect, and the rights of communities to access remedies, in the context of nickel mining in Raja Ampat. This gap becomes an important space for further research.

A literature review on nickel mining in Raja Ampat also shows that this issue encompasses ethical, technical, socio-ecological, and legal dimensions, but it is still underexplored from a global human rights perspective. Sani and Syamsuddin (2025) highlight the importance of environmental ethics by rejecting anthropocentrism and emphasizing the moral obligation to protect the marine ecosystem of Raja Ampat as part of humans' ethical responsibility to nature. Nurdin and Pangkung (2020) focus on technical aspects, particularly the effectiveness of mining drainage systems in reducing runoff and environmental impact. Rahma et al. (2025) show that nickel mining creates social and ecological vulnerabilities for indigenous communities dependent on marine resources, while Wijaya (2025) reveals the weak legal framework and the limited participation of indigenous communities in the mining permitting process. Although these four studies provide important sectoral insights, the research is fragmented and has not yet employed the UNGPs analytical framework that emphasizes three main pillars: the state's duty to protect, the corporate responsibility to respect, and access to remedy for victims of human rights abuses.

Studies related to the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs), such as the works of Muchlinski (2021), Supriyadhie and Rahayu (2017), Luthfan and Hastarini (2022), and Liu (2023), mostly focus on corporate attitude changes, state obligations, legal harmonization, and the implementation of Human Rights Due Diligence (HRDD). However, most of these studies are normative in nature and have not explored the empirical context in the extractive sector, including nickel mining in Raja Ampat. None of these studies analyzed mining operations within conservation areas in Indonesia, thus failing to depict the practical implementation of the three core pillars of the UNGPs: the state's duty

to protect, the corporate responsibility to respect, and access to remedy, in the context of natural resource conflicts and the rights of indigenous communities. Therefore, this research identifies significant gaps and offers novelty through the empirical application and evaluation of the UNGPs in the nickel mining sector in Raja Ampat, using a multi-level approach that connects legal, corporate, and community perspectives.

This literature review also helps identify the lack of integrated research combining three main variables: human rights violations in the mining industry, nickel mining in Raja Ampat, and the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs). Therefore, this study synthesizes these three variables to examine how and why human rights violations occur in the case of nickel mining in Raja Ampat and to analyze the extent to which the UNGPs are applied in this context.

This research uses a qualitative method with a case study approach supported by a literature review from academic journals, reports, and documents related to nickel mining in Raja Ampat within the period of 2020 to 2025. The conceptual framework used in this study is based on the Business and Human Rights concept developed by John Ruggie (2013), which links corporate activities with human rights principles to ensure that companies respect and are accountable for any human rights violations caused, whether directly or indirectly (Ruggie, 2013; Asriasni, 2024). The framework emphasizes three main components: respect for human rights, human rights due diligence, and remediation. Companies, as entities that derive the greatest economic benefit, have a responsibility to uphold international human rights standards, assess their business practices through due diligence, and provide access to remedy mechanisms for affected parties (Ruggie, 2013; United Nations, 2011; Asriasni, 2024). Ruggie's Business and Human Rights concept was institutionalized in the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs) through three main pillars: (1) the state's duty to protect human rights, (2) corporate responsibility to respect human rights, and (3) access to remedies for victims of human rights violations. These three pillars serve as the analytical framework in this study.

Figure 1.2

Conceptual Framework

(Source: Ruggie, 2013; United Nations, 2011; Asriasni, 2024; processed by the author)

The structure of this research begins with the introduction section, which outlines the background of the problem, the relevance of the study, research gaps, as well as conceptual

explanations. The second section discusses the research methodology, explaining the approaches used, data collection methods, and analysis techniques. The third section, which is the research results, presents the data obtained during the research process. The fourth section, the discussion, elaborates on the main findings. This section is divided into three subsections: The State's Obligation to Protect Human Rights, Corporate Responsibility to Respect Human Rights, and Access to Remedies for Victims of Human Rights Violations.

Methods

The research method used in this study is a descriptive qualitative approach, which aims to provide an in-depth understanding of human rights violations occurring in nickel mining practices in Raja Ampat, Papua. This approach was chosen because it can comprehensively depict the social, political, and economic contexts that shape the interactions between the state, corporations, and local communities in the implementation of business and human rights principles.

This research takes the form of a case study and documentary study, focusing on nickel mining projects in the Raja Ampat region. The study relies entirely on secondary data, making the document selection process a crucial aspect in maintaining the quality of the analysis. The author selects documents for analysis based on their relevance to nickel mining and human rights issues, the credibility of the publishing institution, and the recency of the information. The sources used include Indonesian mining policy documents, company reports, records from environmental and human rights activists, third-party reported community interviews, documentary videos, academic journal articles, and news reports related to nickel mining activities in Raja Ampat during the period 2020 to 2025.

To ensure the validity of the data, this study employed triangulation techniques by comparing and verifying information from various sources to obtain credible and reliable findings. Nevertheless, the use of secondary data has limitations, such as potential bias from the reporting parties, reliance on available documentation, and the possibility of unpublished or inaccessible information. These limitations are acknowledged as part of the research design and are taken into account in the process of interpreting the findings.

The independent variable in this study is the implementation of business principles and human rights in the context of nickel mining in Raja Ampat. Meanwhile, the dependent variable is the extent to which the three pillars of the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs)—namely the duty to protect, respect, and remedy—are applied in practice by the state and corporations. Through this approach, this study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the responsibilities of the state and companies in protecting, respecting, and remedying the rights of affected communities in accordance with the UNGPs framework.

Results

The findings of this study indicate that nickel mining activities in Raja Ampat, Indonesia, have resulted in human rights violations related to the right to a healthy

environment, the rights of Indigenous peoples, and the right to participate in decision-making processes. Based on the analysis of national and regional policy documents on mining and human rights, human rights organization reports, and community interview data, it was found that the processes of exploration and exploitation were carried out without an adequate mechanism of Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC) from the Indigenous communities.

National and regional policies related to mining and human rights explicitly emphasize environmental protection and the upholding of human rights principles. Several key regulations—five in total—were identified and are presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1
Regulations on Mining and Human Rights in Indonesia

National/Regional Regulation	Key Provisions	Relevance to the Nickel Mining Case in Raja Ampat
Law No. 39 of 1999 on Human Rights	The state is obliged to respect, protect, and fulfill human rights.	Serves as a legal basis for identifying human rights violations, including environmental rights, public participation, and community welfare.
Law No. 32 of 2009 on Environmental Protection and Management	Regulates Environmental Impact Assessments, environmental permits, sanctions for polluters, and citizens' rights to a healthy environment.	Violations of environmental permits and ecological damage from mining can be categorized as violations of the right to a healthy environment.
Law No. 3 of 2020 on Mineral and Coal Mining	Regulates licensing, reclamation, corporate social responsibility, and environmental management in mining operations.	Relevant for assessing corporate compliance with reclamation and social responsibility obligations.
National Human Rights Action Plan 2021–2025	National agenda for integrating human rights into development policy.	Serves as a policy instrument to assess the state's fulfillment of its duty to protect human rights in the mining sector.
West Papua Provincial Regulation No. 4 of 2019 on Sustainable Development in Papua	Establishes West Papua as a conservation province and guarantees Indigenous peoples' rights to natural resources.	Provides the regional policy foundation that conflicts with nickel mining activities in the Raja Ampat conservation area.

Thus, the national and regional regulatory framework demonstrates normative progress in line with the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs). However, there are still significant gaps between the normative provisions and their practical implementation, particularly regarding law enforcement, licensing transparency, and recovery mechanisms for affected communities. Reports from environmental and human

rights organizations reveal severe ecological impacts, including damage to mangrove forests, marine sedimentation, and water pollution, all of which threaten the livelihoods of coastal communities. The report *Paradise Lost? How Nickel Mining Threatens the Future of Raja Ampat* by Greenpeace Indonesia (2025) documents the existence of 16 nickel mining permits in the Raja Ampat area, 12 of which are located within the UNESCO Global Geopark, and 10 of which overlap with protected forests or conservation zones. Mining activities—especially on Gag and Kawe Islands—have caused deforestation, marine sedimentation, and water pollution, directly impacting marine ecosystem damage and ecotourism-based livelihoods (Greenpeace Indonesia, 2025).

Figure 3.1
Map of Nickel Mining Operation Areas in Raja Ampat
 (Source: Greenpeace, 2025)

The expansion of nickel mining activities in Raja Ampat, particularly by PT Mulia Raymond Perkasa (MRP) in the Central Raja Ampat area, has sparked growing concerns among local communities, tourism industry players, and conservation activists. Public opposition has been expressed through protest actions organized by local residents as well as petitions submitted by the Raja Ampat Nature Protection Alliance to local authorities, demanding the halt of the planned mining operations. Support for these protests also came from the Raja Ampat Local Homestay Association, the Professional Divers Association, the Indonesian Tour Guide Association, and the Local Boat Owners Association, who together sent official letters to the Minister of Environment and Forestry, the Regent of Raja Ampat, and other relevant officials at the beginning of 2025. This collective attitude reflects a shared awareness of the potential ecological and social damage that nickel mining activities can cause. The Indonesian Hotel and Restaurant Association (PHRI) also emphasizes the importance of maintaining sustainable ecotourism in the area, in line with the call for responsible resource management and environmental conservation (Greenpeace Indonesia, 2025).

Table 3.2*The Evidance of Human Rights Violance in Raja Ampat Mining*

Related Rights	Form of Violation	Evidence of Violation Provided
The Right to a Healthy Environment and Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Damage to marine and terrestrial ecosystems (deforestation, water pollution, marine sedimentation) due to mining activities. - Degradation of coral reefs and marine life that threaten the livelihoods of coastal communities (fish, marine life, tourism). 	<p>Greenpeace. (2025). Paradise Lost? How nickel mining threatens the future of one of the world's most important biodiversity hotspots. Greenpeace Indonesia (June 2025).</p> <p>Samadi, Yudi. (2025). National Human Rights Commission Highlights Environmental Human Rights Violations Due to Nickel Mining in Raja Ampat. Sonara.co.id. di Raja Ampat. Sonara.co.id.</p>
Rights of Indigenous/Local Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mining activities are carried out without the legitimate approval of indigenous communities (no Free, Prior, Informed Consent mechanism). - Marginalization of indigenous peoples and local communities; risk of social conflict due to lack of participation and transparency. 	<p>Human Rights Monitor. (2025). Environmental Destructions and Indigenous Rights Violations: The Nickel Mining Crisis in Raja Ampat. Human Rights Monitor (4 July 2025).</p> <p>Irawan, 2020; Purba, 2021 in Sah, Firman., Satria, Hendy. (2025). Business Ethics Violations in Nickel Mining Activities in Raja Ampat: An Analysis of Social and Environmental Impacts. Jurnal Pustakka Nusantara Multidisiplin.</p>
Participatory Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local / indigenous communities are not adequately involved in permit consultations or decision-making; information about impacts, locations, and permits is not available transparently. - Residents who oppose the mine are vulnerable to intimidation, marginalization, and social conflict, indicating violations of the rights to freedom of expression and participation. 	<p>Human Rights Monitor. (2025). Environmental Destruction and Indigenous Rights Violations: The Nickel Mining Crisis in Raja Ampat. Human Rights Monitor (4 July 2025).</p> <p>Sah, Firman., Satria, Hendy. (2025). Business Ethics Violations in Nickel Mining Activities in Raja Ampat: An Analysis of Social and Environmental Impacts. Jurnal Pustaka Nusantara Multidisiplin.</p>

The resistance carried out by the people of Raja Ampat, and more broadly by the Indonesian public, managed to influence government policy. The Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (ESDM) issued Press Release No. 054.Pers/KM.01.03/SJI/2025 on June 10,

2025, announcing the revocation of four Mining Business Licenses (IUP) in Raja Ampat. The revocations were carried out on the grounds that these companies did not comply with environmental regulations. The four companies whose IUPs were revoked are PT Anugerah Surya Pratama (ASP), PT Mulia Raymond Perkasa (MRP), PT Kawei Sejahtera Mining (KSM), and PT Nurham. Furthermore, the Ministry explained that the issuance of these licenses occurred before the designation of Raja Ampat as a UNESCO Geopark in 2023 (ESDM, 2025). However, in its implementation, the government appeared to apply selective measures, as one state-owned company—PT Gag Nickel—was still allowed to retain its operational license (Puspita & Ariyani, 2025).

Responding to this matter, the Chairman of the Indonesian Mining Experts Association (PERHAPI), Sudirman Widhy Hartono, stated that the government’s decision is believed to have gone through careful consideration. Nevertheless, he urged the government to be more selective in issuing mining permits in the future to prevent further revocations that could negatively impact the investment climate in Indonesia's mining sector. A Tempo report dated September 10, 2025, revealed that after being temporarily suspended, PT Gag Nickel resumed operations in Raja Ampat. This development has caused disappointment among the 60,000 people who signed a petition opposing nickel mining in the area (Hasyim & Wuragil, 2025). These findings indicate that the government's commitment to environmental compliance remains questionable.

Figure 3.2
Map of the Raja Ampat Geopark Area
 (Source: Greenpeace, 2025)

The exemption of PT Gag Nickel from the revocation of its mining permit is based on several considerations. The Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources, Bahlil Lahadalia, after

conducting an evaluation in the Raja Ampat mining area, explained that PT Gag Nickel's IUP was not revoked because the exploration process was considered to have been carried out correctly and met the Environmental Impact Analysis (AMDAL) requirements. Furthermore, Bahlil stated that PT Gag Nickel's mining location is not within the Geopark area, but rather closer to the North Maluku region, about 42 kilometers from the area designated as a UNESCO Geopark. Based on field observations, PT Gag Nickel holds a mining license covering 13,000 hectares on Gag Island, an area that even exceeds the size of the island itself, which is only 6,030 hectares. Of the total area, about 260 hectares have been opened for exploitation activities. To date, around 130 hectares have been reclaimed, with approximately 54 hectares of the rehabilitation area returned to the state. Meanwhile, about 130 hectares remain active production areas and are planned to be reclaimed after mining operations are completed (Nugraheny & Djumena, 2025). The fact that PT Gag Nickel is part of state assets, managed by a subsidiary of PT Aneka Tambang (Antam) Tbk., cannot be overlooked as an important factor in the government's decision not to revoke the company's mining license.

The government's obligation to ensure that mining activities comply with regulatory mechanisms and human rights is crucial. Four companies whose mining business licenses (IUP) were revoked are required to carry out environmental and social recovery efforts to address the impacts of their operations. The Ministry of Environment conducted inspections from May 26–31, 2025, revealing significant ecosystem damage in Raja Ampat due to exploration activities by three companies, namely ASP, KSM, and MRP, while PT Nurham was not assessed as it had not started operations. In addition, Minister of Environment Hanif Faisol emphasized that small islands like those in Raja Ampat should not be used as mining sites, as this contradicts Law No. 1 of 2014 on the Management of Coastal Areas and Small Islands (PWP3K) (Saturi, 2025).

Discussion

Nickel mining in Raja Ampat, Papua, clearly illustrates how the dynamics of economic development in resource-rich regions often intersect with complex human rights issues. On one hand, the nickel mining industry promises development and national economic contributions through increased investment and job opportunities. On the other hand, this expansion also gives rise to various structural problems, including land conflicts, environmental degradation, and violations of the rights of indigenous communities who have historical and spiritual ties to their land and sea territories.

In this context, the framework of the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs) becomes highly relevant for assessing the extent to which states and corporations fulfill their obligations and responsibilities to protect, respect, and remedy violated rights. The UNGPs provide a conceptual framework that emphasizes that sustainable business practices cannot be separated from respect for human dignity and principles of social justice. This framework stands on three interrelated pillars: the state's duty to protect, the corporate responsibility to respect, and access to remedy for affected communities. These three pillars are not separate entities but interconnected components that together form a normative foundation for human rights-based business governance.

1. The State's Duty to Protect Human Rights

As the main actor in the international system, the state holds a fundamental obligation to protect human rights from violations committed by third parties, including corporations. This principle is not only derived from constitutional duties, but also represents a moral and political commitment enshrined in various international human rights instruments. In the context of the nickel mining industry in Raja Ampat, this obligation requires the state to ensure that all licensing, monitoring, and evaluation processes of business activities are carried out in a transparent, accountable, and participatory manner.

However, practices in the field often show the limitations of the state's capacity as well as a lack of impartiality in carrying out its protective functions. The state tends to act more as an investment facilitator rather than as a regulator ensuring compliance with human rights principles. When the Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC) mechanism is not implemented genuinely, violations of indigenous peoples' rights occur even at the planning stage. This indicates a gap in accountability between national development policies and the state's obligation to protect its citizens.

In the case of nickel mining in Raja Ampat, this study found that Indonesia's national policies have not fully served as the main reference for the government in issuing mining permits. The government failed to conduct an administrative review of the mining area before issuing permits, thus violating Law No. 1 of 2014 on the Management of Coastal Areas and Small Islands (PWP3K). In addition, the national regulations listed in Table 2.1 were also implemented weakly. Although the government eventually revoked the IUPs of four companies, the fact that human rights and environmental violations had already occurred raises a critical question: would the government conduct an evaluation if there were no public opposition to mining activities in Raja Ampat?

Within the framework of the UNGPs, a state's failure to fulfill its duty to protect reflects an inability to internalize human rights as an integral part of economic policy. As a result, policies that should ensure a balance between economic interests and social justice instead widen the gap between corporations and local communities.

2. Corporate Responsibility to Respect Human Rights

The second pillar of the UNGPs emphasizes that corporations have an independent responsibility to respect human rights, regardless of the extent to which the state fulfills its own obligations. This principle reflects the idea that business actors are not merely economic entities but also ethical agents who must ensure that their operations do not cause harm to people or the environment. In the context of nickel mining in Raja Ampat, this responsibility includes the implementation of Human Rights Due Diligence (HRDD), a process to identify, prevent, mitigate, and account for potential human rights violations.

However, in practice, due diligence is often conducted formalistically, with the main focus on fulfilling administrative requirements rather than substantive human rights

accountability. When companies limit their obligations to compliance with legal documents without considering the social and cultural impacts on local communities, the essence of human rights responsibility becomes hollow.

Empirical findings show that only one in four companies holding Mining Business Licenses (IUP) in Raja Ampat meet the Environmental Impact Assessment (AMDAL) requirements and carry out reclamation activities. Nevertheless, the ongoing environmental damage and the disruption of local tourism economic stability indicate deeper structural issues in corporate accountability. Revoking mining licenses does not automatically absolve companies of their responsibility to respect human rights. This obligation should not depend on public pressure or state intervention; rather, it must stem from the company's internal awareness that human rights are an ethical foundation for sustainable business practices.

3. Access to Remedy for Victims of Human Rights Violations

The third pillar of the UNGPs emphasizes that the existence of effective remedy mechanisms is a prerequisite for a substantive human rights protection system. These mechanisms must ensure that victims of violations can obtain justice through both judicial and non-judicial avenues that are accessible, fair, predictable, and transparent. In the context of nickel mining, local communities often face various obstacles in seeking redress for the harms they experience—whether due to environmental damage or the loss of traditional livelihoods. These obstacles are not only procedural, such as difficulties in accessing judicial institutions, but also structural, reflecting power imbalances between corporations and affected communities.

Non-judicial mechanisms, which ideally can function as alternatives, such as mediation or complaint submission institutions, are often ineffective due to a lack of independence and transparency. Recovery from the impacts of mining should not be understood merely as an administrative matter, but must encompass environmental, social, and economic dimensions that directly affect community welfare.

4. Strengthening Impact through Long-Term Policy Innovation

One important aspect that needs to be reinforced in the context of the findings of this research is the development of long-term policies that systematically prevent the recurrence of human rights violations and environmental damage in nickel mining practices, particularly in conservation areas such as Raja Ampat. Although the government has responded to public pressure by revoking several mining business licenses (IUP), these actions remain reactive and do not yet reflect structural changes in national mining governance. Therefore, a long-term policy approach is needed, which includes: (1) Restructuring mining licensing governance through a verification mechanism based on transparency, independent audits, and the obligation to make IUP data publicly available; (2) Strengthening a legally binding FPIC framework, not merely as an administrative procedure, but as a mandatory prerequisite that determines whether a mining permit in indigenous territories is valid or not; (3) Developing science- and human rights-based conservation policies, which affirm the ban on exploration and exploitation in geoparks, conservation areas, and small islands; (4)

Implementation of long-term remediation mechanisms that require companies to finance ecological restoration as well as social compensation for affected communities, including environmental recovery fund schemes managed independently; and (5) Integration of UNGPs principles into national and regional development plans, so that the protection, respect, and restoration of community rights do not depend on public pressure, but are embedded in the design of state policies.

Through the development of this long-term policy framework, this research not only reveals the violations that have occurred but also provides a strategic contribution to mining governance reform and the protection of human rights in Indonesia. Innovative, long-term-oriented policies will ensure that exploitative practices do not recur, while guaranteeing the sustainability of ecosystems and the well-being of local communities over time.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Analysis based on the three pillars of the UNGPs shows that the core issue in the nickel mining industry in Raja Ampat does not lie solely at the policy level, but in the absence of a human rights-based development paradigm. Both the state and corporations still operate within an extractive economic framework that prioritizes efficiency and growth, while neglecting human and ecological sustainability.

In addition, the UNGPs emphasize the importance of synergy between the state, corporations, and civil society. The state must not allow corporations to operate without ethical oversight, and corporations cannot claim social legitimacy without a genuine commitment to human rights. Meanwhile, civil society functions as a moral watchdog, ensuring that development efforts do not neglect humanitarian values. Thus, the success of UNGPs implementation is measured not only by the extent to which violations can be prevented, but also by how effectively the relationship between the business world and society is built on a foundation of justice, equality, and respect for human dignity.

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